

Relationship between Dimensions of Self-consciousness and Emotional Regulation among Young Adults

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Self-consciousness reveals the attention that young adults pay to their own feelings, thoughts, and emotions. It also delves into one's thought patterns regarding what they consider others think about them. Emotional regulation, on the other hand, plays a crucial role in how one deals with the emotions stemming from these thoughts. Indian studies have not been conducted enough to focus on studying the relationship between the dimensions of self-consciousness and emotional regulation. Hence, the present study is an attempt to study the relationship between dimensions of two covert aspects of psychological systems: self-consciousness and emotional regulation, by administering two reliable psychological tools on 112 young adults to measure, using a correlation design. The results showed that in young adults' reappraisal was positively correlated with private and public self-consciousness and suppression had a positive correlation only with public self-consciousness. No significant correlation of social anxiety with reappraisal and suppression was reported. The present study has highlighted that young adults use emotional regulation methods in an adaptive way. They focus more on re-interpreting emotions rather than suppressing them, and this leads to lesser social anxiety, more awareness of their thoughts, emotions and feelings and what they consider others think of them. This study can be used to form interventions and gain insights about consciousness and emotional regulation of young adults.

Keywords: Self-consciousness, emotional regulation, social anxiety, psychological systems

Self-consciousness and emotional regulation are the integral aspects of the covert systems of human psychology, as they are related to others, however not visible to or hidden from others. Their relationship defines the capability and confidence with which one reaches out to fulfil various developmental growth at different life stages. This is specifically crucial for the youth as they undergo major life changes in the psychological system, which encapsulates personal growth, relationship formation, career formation, temper and emotional formation, and all of these are influenced by Self-consciousness and Emotional Regulation. Self-consciousness could be defined as the tendency of an individual to habitually draw attention towards the internal systems of oneself, primarily, towards how one thinks they are appearing in front of others, i.e., public self-consciousness, and of their own internal system of thoughts, emotions, feelings, i.e., private self-consciousness and being uncomfortable in social situations, i.e., social anxiety (Scheier & Carver, 1985). This multi-dimensional system is not necessarily negative or positive; rather, it can be both helpful and unhelpful. Emotional Regulation refers to the processes through which an individual manages emotions consciously. This is done in two ways: Reappraisal and Suppression. Reappraisal is a system where one re-

interprets an experience in order to alter its impact on the emotions; while suppression refers to holding back the expression of emotions that others can notice, like any visible signs (Gross & John, 2003).

Ahadzadeh et al. (2021) studied the impact of self-consciousness on self-monitoring on Instagram on university students and it revealed that private self-consciousness doesn't directly predict self-monitoring on Instagram. Relationship of private self-consciousness and self-esteem was studied in Noida, India, where results depicted that social anxiety had a significant correlation and was a strong predictor of low self-esteem and self-efficacy (Chakladar & Rawat, 2020). The classification of public and private self-consciousness has been supported by a study done on 602 young adults by DaSilveira et al. (2015). Oriyama et al. (2025) study indicated that with respect to age, young adults had a higher ability to regulate emotions than older adults through reappraisal; use of suppression did not differ by age. Emotion regulation is more helpful when strategies are flexibly applied and are based on context rather than rigidly classified as positive or negative (Blanke et al., 2020). A study by Yildiz (2017) found that maladaptive emotion regulation strategies have shown to predict Internet and smartphone addiction in adolescents. In another study, adolescents with trauma reported significantly more emotion regulation difficulties, and targeted interventions were highlighted (Villalta et al., 2018). Daly et al. (2015) observed that Yoga significantly enhances emotional regulation in adolescents and positive results were reflected in mindfulness, self-compassion, and body awareness.

Rationale of the Study

The present study is vital as there is a need to comprehend the emotional domain of the youth, specifically in relation to how they think they appear in front of others and the strategies they use in order to regulate emotions consciously. It offers valuable insights about self-perception, emotional coping, relationship patterns, and communication and expression strategies of the young adults.

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Research Gap

Self-consciousness and emotional regulation have been studied separately and there is limited research on how they relate to each other among youth in context to Indian population. Previous studies have also not explored the relationship between types of self-consciousness: public, private and social anxiety and emotional regulation: reappraisal and suppression. Therefore, the present study covers the gap and gives a holistic insight.

Problem

To study the relationship between types of self-consciousness: public, private and social anxiety with emotional regulation strategies: reappraisal and suppression among young adults.

Hypothesis of the Study

There is a positive correlation of types of self-consciousness: public, private and social anxiety with emotional regulation strategies: reappraisal and suppression.

Method

Participants

The present study was conducted on 112 young adults (18-25 years) which constituted of 91 females and 21 males, residing in and around Agra, who have completed at least their intermediate education. They were selected through convenience sampling.

Variables

Predictor Variable: Types of self-consciousness: public, private and social anxiety.

Criterion Variable: Emotional regulation strategies: reappraisal and suppression.

Research Design

Correlational research design has been used in the present study.

Measures

Self-consciousness Scale-Revised (SCS-R) by Scheier and Carver (1985): It is a 4-point Likert scale with 22 items divided into three subscales: private self-consciousness, public self-consciousness and social anxiety. Cronbach's alpha values typically range from 0.74 to 0.84 across subscales. Significant correlation was found between public self-consciousness, correlating positively with social anxiety ($r = 0.50$) and negatively with self-esteem ($r = -0.30$), while private self-consciousness correlates moderately with introspective tendencies ($r = 0.40$) (Scheier & Carver, 1985; Trapnell & Campbell, 1999).

Emotion Regulation Questionnaire by Gross and John (2003): It is a 7-point Likert scale with 10 items rated on a six-item targeting reappraisal and four items targeting suppression. Cronbach's alpha values range from 0.73 to 0.82 across subscales, and is a confirmed two-factor structure through factor analyses. Construct validity was established with cognitive reappraisal positively correlated with positive affect ($r = 0.42$) and life satisfaction ($r = 0.30$), and negatively with negative affect ($r = 0.51$). Expressive suppression shows negative correlations with positive affect ($r = 0.33$) and life satisfaction ($r = 0.34$), and a positive correlation with negative affect ($r = 0.39$) (Gross & John, 2003).

Procedure

In the present study, participants were selected on the basis of their location, age and educational qualification. They were informed about the purpose of the study and consent was taken before filling out the form. After they filled out the form, the data was analysed. Ethical considerations were rigorously followed.

Results

Table 1
Descriptive Statistics for Self-consciousness

	Private Self Consciousness	Public Self Consciousness	Social Anxiety	Reappraisal	Suppression
N	112	112	112	112	112
Mean	16.6	12.4	9.77	4.79	4.60
Median	17.0	12.0	9.00	4.83	4.50
Standard deviation	4.70	4.51	3.95	1.04	1.11

Table 1 is the descriptive analysis of the sample ($N = 112$). Participants reported a higher level of private self-consciousness ($M = 16.6, SD = 4.70$) and a moderate level of public self-consciousness ($M = 12.4, SD = 4.51$). Social anxiety was lower ($M = 9.77, SD = 3.95$). Further, participants reported more frequency in using reappraisal ($M = 4.79, SD = 1.04$) than use of suppression ($M = 4.60,$

$SD = 1.11$). This represents that young adults are highly engaged in what they think about their feelings, emotions and thoughts, moderately engaged in what they think others think of them, and are less engaged in being uncomfortable around others. Further, they regulate emotions more by re-interpreting emotions, which is adaptive and relatively less by hiding them.

Table 2
Correlation Matrix

	Private Self-consciousness	Public Self-Consciousness	Social Anxiety
Reappraisal Pearson's r	0.378***	0.263**	-0.127
Suppression Pearson's r	0.014	0.199*	0.083

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Table 2 displays the correlation matrix. The results show that reappraisal is significantly and positively correlated with private self-consciousness ($r = 0.378, p < 0.001$) and public self-consciousness ($r = 0.263, p < 0.01$). This relationship indicates that young adults with higher private self-consciousness tend to use reappraisal more often as an emotion regulation strategy, and both of these are adaptive. They also employ reinterpreting emotions for what they think others think about them. However, it is less than using reappraisal for what they think about themselves. However, reappraisal is not significantly related to social anxiety ($r = -0.127, p > 0.05$). Which means that young adults who reinterpret emotions to reframe situations positively do not report significant social anxiety. No significant relationships were found between suppression with private self-consciousness ($r = 0.014$) and social anxiety ($r = 0.083$). This represents that individuals who are conscious about their own feelings, emotions and thoughts are not likely to be uncomfortable in public spaces and hide their emotions from others. Suppression shows a significantly positive correlation with public self-consciousness ($r = 0.199, p < 0.05$). This implies that if individuals are thinking about themselves on the basis of how others view them, they are likely to suppress visible signs of emotions.

Discussion

On the basis of the statistical analysis, the findings suggest that the hypothesis formulated that there is a positive correlation between types of self-consciousness (private, public, & social anxiety) and emotion regulation strategies (reappraisal & suppression), is partially accepted. Significant positive correlation is found between private and public self-consciousness and reappraisal. Positive correlation is found between public self-consciousness and suppression. However, no significant correlation is found between social anxiety and reappraisal or suppression, and between private self-consciousness and suppression. Reappraisal is more frequently used than suppression, and there is the highest private self-consciousness, followed by public self-consciousness and the least social anxiety. The present study highlights that higher private and public self-conscious is significantly positively related to adaptive emotional regulation. Specifically, young adults who use cognitive reappraisal are more engaged in private self-consciousness, followed by public self-consciousness.

The findings of the present study are supported by previous researches, reappraisal was compared with strategies like distraction and suppression, and it had more adaptive emotional outcomes than others (McRae, 2016). Reappraisal was more effective than expressive suppression in reducing negative emotions based on self-reports, while physiological measures showed no significant difference (Mohammed, Kosonogov, & Lyusin, 2021). There are several factors, like resilience, that positively impact self-consciousness, both directly and indirectly via factors like self-esteem and positive affect (Ren & Chen, 2022) these could be factors that strengthen the relationship between public and private self-consciousness and reappraisal. Self-consciousness is negatively linked to depression, while life meaningfulness and self-efficacy partially mediate this relationship (Yuan et al., 2024). These studies also depict that there is an adaptive impact of the relationship between public and private self-consciousness with reappraisal.

Conclusion

This study has provided evidence for future research and the formation of theories that could focus on qualitatively understanding the reasons why reappraisal is used more often for public and private self-consciousness. It could also be studied from a developmental perspective which factors made an individual choose a particular strategy. Interventions related to emotional regulation could be applied to young adults who reported suppression and social anxiety. These interventions could include acceptance and commitment therapy, spiritual cognitive behavioural therapy to name a few.

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